

ARCTIC PASSION

Dissemination Plan

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Work package

09 - Connecting the PAN-AOSS with society through communication, dissemination and engagement

Lead beneficiary

13 - GRID-Arendal

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2023-08-10	2.0	Revised version 2.0 submitted: A new section on intellectual property rights (2.4.3) added; Number of Indigenous People’s Partner Communities and co-creation of posters changed in Table 1; Note about Horizon Results Booster’ services added in Section 2.4; Section 2.4.5 on Intellectual property rights added: More qualitative indicators included in Table 5; Windows to the Arctic updated to Arctic Window throughout the document	Sabrina Heerema and Anna Sinisalo, GRID-Arendal; Lisa Grosfeld, AWI

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Executive summary

The Arctic PASSION Dissemination Plan explains how dissemination and utilisation activities differ from communication activities and the goal for those activities. It explains the expected results of the project, as well as the strategy for achieving dissemination of those results.

The plan presents the dissemination and Utilisation measures and channels that are planned to use strategically for the various target groups of the project. All of the dissemination channels and platforms that Arctic PASSION plans to use are listed, as well as a calendar overview of when events may occur. The risks and barriers to the realization of the project's results have been considered and mitigation strategies proposed. The highest risks are constraints due to COVID-19 related issues.

Project partners are asked to regularly log any and all publications, communications or dissemination activities in activity trackers, in order to effectively monitor the impact of the project, as well as for regular reporting purposes. The main Dissemination & Utilisation Activities expected of each work package are specified here. The Project Management Office is responsible for collating and submitting these impact reports, however, Work Package 9 is responsible for monitoring other key performance indicators related to the impact of the various communication and dissemination tools.

Work Package 9 supported by the Project Management Office is responsible for the implementation of this plan, as well as any updates to the plan during the project lifetime.

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1 Introduction

Arctic PASSION stands for 'Pan-Arctic Observing System of Systems (pan-AOSS): Implementing observations for societal needs'. The project aims at creating a coherent, integrated Arctic observing system, suitable for end-user needs and co-created together with local and Indigenous Communities. Further information about the project is available at www.arcticpassion.eu.

To reach the main objective, various types of interactions between Arctic PASSION partners, rights holders and stakeholders and target groups are essential. The strategies and plans for these interactions are specified in four interrelated documents: the Communication Plan, Dissemination & Utilisation Plan, Stakeholder Engagement Plan and Education & Training Plan. This document focuses on the dissemination and Utilisation of the project results. Please refer to the abbreviations list in the Arctic PASSION Communication Plan.

In this document, 'dissemination' and 'utilisation' are defined according to the definitions by Horizon 2020:

"As Horizon 2020 is financed by EU citizens, it should benefit the largest number and the fruits of the research reach society as a whole.

Dissemination: *means sharing research results with potential users - peers in the research field, industry, other commercial players and policymakers. By sharing your research results with the rest of the scientific community, you are contributing to the progress of science in general.*

Utilisation: *is the use of results for commercial purposes or in public policymaking.*1"*

The Communication, Dissemination and Utilisation activities fall under the objective 9 work package, which is described in the proposal as "Establish mutual learning with stakeholders, rights holders, and end-users; communicate, and disseminate project results, and foster the understanding and uptake of our services by end-users. These will include European citizens, scientists, Arctic and Indigenous communities (in local languages), operational agencies, the private and public sectors, and decision-makers at many levels."

¹ We have used 'Utilisation' as a replacement for 'exploitation', which is the official EU term used for use of dissemination results. However, we feel this term is inappropriate for the project as it has negative connotations and may be offensive.

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This plan will be continuously updated in order to meet the objectives of Arctic PASSION.

2. Arctic PASSION’s plan for the dissemination and utilisation of results

2.1 Arctic PASSION results

Arctic PASSION will produce a series of services, tools and other information products that will serve societal needs in the Arctic region. The expected major results of the project include:

- Enhanced Earth Observations (EO) in the Arctic region.
- Definition of Shared Arctic Variables that are best suited to (i) understand the Arctic and predict change, (ii) assess risks and guide mitigation and adaptation measures, (iii) provide essential information for the health and wellbeing of Arctic communities.
- An improved Arctic Data System that will better serve the needs of the data-users, a range of new, improved tools that can serve the needs of the Arctic stakeholders, such as reducing the uncertainty of weather forecasts, or safe ship routing through sea ice.
- New Arctic services to support decision making needs, and to provide easy-to-access information that enables the users to reduce risks.
- Implementation of the first database that combines the vast knowledge of environmental change anchored in the Indigenous and local knowledge of Arctic People with scientific information.
- A more accountable and sustainable pan-Arctic Observing System of Systems (pan-AOSS) will result in a more visible profile for EU Arctic observing activities.
- Communication platforms that are co-developed with the rights-holders and stakeholders to facilitate dialogue between the Arctic residents, decision-makers, scientists and others to ensure an adaptive, iterative and responsive pan-AOSS.
- A stronger European Polar research community and advanced research on the societal and demographic impact of changes in the Arctic.
- Better visibility of Arctic issues in EU policy-making and strengthened participatory governance in the EU.

2.2 Arctic PASSION’s stakeholders and target groups

Arctic PASSION activities will be designed to maximise the impact of the results, and to deliver information to specific groups in the appropriate formats, and at the appropriate time. We intend to engage with groups that were defined previously in section 3 of the Communication plan.

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2.3 Strategy for the dissemination of results

Arctic PASSION will disseminate its results in a series of rights- and stakeholder events, customized training, and conferences and making strategic use of various dissemination and communication channels and platforms. The project's Utilisation strategy relies on the identification of key knowledge outputs (deliverables, publications, datasets, pilot services) to be communicated to targeted audiences using knowledge transfer tools such as those provided by the European Commission.

Through targeted dissemination and Utilisation activities, Arctic PASSION will

- Promote sustained funding for Arctic observations
- Provide policy recommendations regarding environmental protection and sustainable development,
- Inform plans to enhance coordination among national agencies of the Arctic countries and highlight ways in which IK and LK inform the pan-AOSS.

Bi-directional communication channels and platforms (for example, Facebook Messenger, WhatsApp, Skype, as well as the 'live' functionality on Social media channels) will be tested and monitored throughout the project period and the most efficient channels will be identified and activated to embed in the Pilot Services and detail a capacity building and engagement programme to enhance the user uptake of the services.

Dissemination activities carried out in the project will be tracked with a log sheet available on the project's intranet.

2.4 Strategy for the utilisation of Arctic PASSION results

Arctic PASSION will liaise with other Horizon 2020 projects in the EU Polar Cluster to optimise synergies among projects and also increase the efficiency of results Utilisation. [In addition, Arctic PASSION cooperates with the EU Polar Cluster on training for intellectual property rights and other important communication and dissemination topics contributing to the impact of our project, using the European Commission's 'Horizon Results Booster' services.](#)

2.4.1 Utilisation of data

Project results will be disseminated to stakeholder groups at a series of engagement and training events. Work Package 9 will support Work Packages 7 and 8 in facilitating targeted policy dialogues and providing policy briefs. Open access to project activities and outcomes will be ensured via the project website and in the form of flyers, graphics, blogs, vlogs, story maps and fact sheets about the Pilot Services to raise awareness and increase uptake of Pilot Services, datasets and scientific results.

In addition, we will take measures to actively encourage all stakeholder groups to utilise project results. This will be done by pointing towards adequate data and services during expert working group meetings, technical workshops as well as scientific conferences, etc.

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2.4.2 Utilisation of new knowledge

Arctic PASSION will participate actively in the working groups of the Arctic Council to link the research to ongoing and/or planned assessment work. Arctic PASSION participates in Communication Task Group meetings as well as activities by other Task Groups of the EU Polar Cluster.

Arctic PASSION will establish a transdisciplinary partnership on Arctic observations among research and monitoring organisations, Indigenous peoples and local populations, decision-makers, policy and commercial stakeholders. Some of the interactions among these will be facilitated in the form of Expert Panels for the ROADS process, and others as a part of the Pilot Services co-creation. Arctic PASSION will develop mechanisms to continue those fora for interaction into the future such that this partnership will outlive the project.

Together with Arctic PASSION partner EPB, with the Arctic Council, SAON, the AOS and IASC, we will discuss how these communication channels can be made an inherent feature of a pan-AOSS after the project is finished. This will be particularly relevant for the channel that allows people living in the Arctic to have an impact on the pan-AOSS's future development.

Most of the Pilot Services will be continued by their main developers; for the others, long-term hosting by Copernicus or other service providers will be sought out. The modular set-up of the PSs will support easy transfer to other hosts in case that should be desired, e.g. for future enhancement or additional functionality. Project results will be kept accessible and promoted through the ~~'Windows to the Arctic Window'~~ platform to be maintained by GRID-Arendal beyond the project duration. This will provide long-term service for a variety of end-users.

To secure long-term funding for the pan-AOSS, Arctic PASSION will engage with funding agencies, e.g. via the Arctic Funders Forum, with recommendations supported by the Societal Benefit Analysis for the Arctic observing based on the Assessments done in Arctic PASSION. The implementation of an Arctic-GEOSS with SAON will be a cornerstone for the sustainable operation of the pan-AOSS. Arctic People, scientists, policymakers and the private sector will be able to utilise Arctic PASSION's achievements well into the future.

2.4.3 Intellectual property rights

The Arctic PASSION Coordination Team is responsible for the management of intellectual property rights (IPR) for the project. Publications, licensing, patents, and other exploitation of the results will be tracked and collected with specific databases accessible by each partner through intranet. Arctic PASSION supports full and meaningful inclusion of Indigenous Peoples, their knowledge and

expertise, with full recognition and acknowledgement of their intellectual property rights. On the management of the project's intellectual property, the Coordination Team will be supported and advised by the EU project officer and AWI's legal department as defined in the Project Management Plan. The management of intellectual property will follow the Arctic PASSION Consortium Agreement signed by each project partner, in particular with reference to the background included (attachment 1). We will also refer to the European IP Helpdesk's Guide for IP in Horizon 2020 especially in reference to the exploitation (utilisation) of project results.

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2.5 Arctic PASSION’s targeted dissemination measures

Table 1. The measures for dissemination and utilisation of results per target group

	Target group	Dissemination and utilisation measures and channels per target group
1	68 Indigenous partner communities and organisations representing partner communities	<p>Pan-Arctic knowledge exchange involving Indigenous communities and other Arctic residents, actors and decision-makers, facilitating co-design of the pilot services and joint development of the pan-AOSS through:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online and face to face meetings • Arctic PASSION stakeholder meetings • Co-development approach and input during workshops • Arctic PASSION website • Social media, especially Facebook • Alerting local media to events, radio interviews, etc. • Peosters tailor-made for selected each communitiesy through a process of co-creation
2	Representatives/ organisations of indigenous communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Face to face briefings • Interactions during conferences • Policy briefs • Personal letters
3	Indigenous youth	<p>Early career researchers and Arctic youth will be trained during the Arctic PASSION School and their involvement will be maintained during the project as “Arctic PASSION Ambassadors”.</p> <p>Arctic PASSION School participants will produce one-minute videos presenting their scientific background and research to be published on the APECS and Arctic PASSION websites.</p> <p>See Arctic PASSION Training and Education Plan for more details.</p>
4	Local communities, representatives and organisations of local communities	<p>Arctic PASSION website Social media, especially Facebook Alerting local media to events, radio interviews, etc.</p>
5	Arctic youth	<p>AWI-APECS and GRID-Arendal will establish contact with early career researchers (ECR), and SNOW and GINR with youth in Arctic Indigenous communities.</p> <p>Early career researchers and Arctic youth will be trained during the Arctic PASSION School and their involvement will be maintained during the project as “Arctic PASSION Ambassadors”.</p>

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		<p>Arctic PASSION School participants will produce one-minute videos presenting their scientific background and research to be published on the APECS and Arctic PASSION websites.</p> <p>See Arctic PASSION Training and Education Plan for more details.</p>
6	Policy and decision-makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online survey on challenges, questions and needs within the frame of Arctic Observing Systems, distributed to regional and local decision-makers (ULAP). • Dialogue platforms with policy-makers • Policy Briefs: aiming at the local, regional, and European levels. • connection with UNEP and other UN agencies to feed information into the UN system • timely information on the status of the natural environment to global climate policy actors • Newsletter • Pilot service workshops • Side events at Arctic Council (AMAP) meetings
7	European and International organisations such as UNEP, EEA, WMO, Global Cryosphere Watch, the Northern Forum, WWF, UNESCO and other environmental agencies and science policy organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Signature publication series to create awareness of emerging issues • GRID-Arendal maintains a strong connection with UNEP and other UN agencies through an ongoing dialogue with their Environment & Climate department, with the possibility to feed information into the UN system and achieve a global level of dissemination. For instance, by sharing Arctic PASSION pilot services with GRID-Geneva, who can use this data in their 'World Environment Situation Room'; Contributions to the UNEP Global Assessments; suggestions for results that can be relevant to fit into their work plan.
8	Local and global non-governmental organisations, non-profit organisations and associations	Publication series on emerging issues
9	<p>Scientific community:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early-career scientists • Science organisations such as ISAC, IASC • Research Institutes • Research projects, programmes and networks • International research projects and programmes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific articles • Scientific conferences • Online Seminars • Meeting with other EU Cluster projects • Summer schools and training through APECS • Media

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU Polar Cluster members 	
10	Arctic PASSION Consortium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Arctic PASSION website • Social media • “Windows to the Arctic <u>Window</u>” platform • Event Activities, booths • Newsletter
11	Observation services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ‘Arctic Window <u>Windows to the Arctic</u>’ online platform • developing pilot services in collaboration with Copernicus services, ESA and Norwegian, Finnish and Danish national ice services
12	Private sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expert groups to identify EAVs • Pilot service workshops
13	Further end-users of the Pilot services	“ Windows to the Arctic <u>Window</u> ” platform
14	European Commission	Event activities. newsletter
15	Media	Media package and press releases
16	General public / Beneficiary population in the Arctic States	Website, social media

2.6 Arctic PASSION’s dissemination channels and platforms

Arctic PASSION makes use of its multiple communication channels and platforms to disseminate results. All communication channels are specified in the Arctic PASSION Communication Plan. However, the channels and platforms that are especially relevant for dissemination and Utilisation purposes are also further clarified below.

Arctic PASSION website (arcticpassion.eu): The website serves both external and internal stakeholders. It will be updated regularly with news about the project’s progress, latest results and linked to the tools and services that Arctic PASSION creates. We will create a collaboratively edited online repository for our project outputs to facilitate sustainable knowledge management and provide one-stop access to project information and data.

Social media: Social media allows Arctic PASSION to reach an extremely wide - but also targeted - audience, maximising the impact and successful Utilisation of our research results. We will make strategic use of social media channels, using them in a purposeful way. The Arctic PASSION Communication Plan outlines the most efficient channels for specific target groups that will also be used for dissemination. Social media outputs will include videos, blogs, graphics and animations produced for rights- and stakeholder meetings, conferences, workshops and training activities and developed for and with community partners.

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Online seminar series: We will provide online training through online seminars on all topics of the Pilot Services, with a special emphasis on Indigenous and Local Knowledge. The online seminars will be recorded and available with open access on the Arctic PASSION and APECS websites. See details in the Arctic PASSION Training and Education Plan.

Rights- and stakeholder engagement events: We will co-create and fund a large number of events to include in dialogues with Rights holders and stakeholders. See Arctic PASSION Stakeholder Engagement Plan.

Dialogues with policy-makers to keep abreast of policy needs and communicate policy recommendations from Arctic PASSION. See Arctic PASSION Stakeholder Engagement Plan.

Policy Briefs: Dialogue with policy-makers and the EC will be used to identify the most relevant topics for policy briefs that we will produce aiming at the local, regional, and European levels.

[Posters: Informative posters about the pilot services focusing on local information and results for the specific community that are most highly requested or interesting for them, in local or Indigenous languages, showing information that only Arctic PASSION can provide ~~that is not existing elsewhere~~.](#)

Newsletters: Our quarterly project newsletter will provide partners, rights- and stakeholders and the general public with relevant information regarding Arctic PASSION activities and developments, including highlighting important results that have been published. Articles will be also submitted to other relevant newsletters, such as EU Polar Cluster, EUPolarNet2, INTERACT, JUSTNORTH, and SAON.

Papers in peer-reviewed journals: We will publish Arctic PASSION results in peer-reviewed scientific journals to reach the scientific community. Targeted journals range from interdisciplinary ones (e.g. AMBIO, Arctic, Nature, Science) to specific (e.g. the Copernicus publications and Frontiers series, Journal of Geophysical Research). The timing of the publications is aimed to align with the input process to the IPCC assessment.

Research blogs: Supported by GRID-Arendal, Arctic PASSION researchers will write short, personal stories from the field shedding light on Arctic PASSION activities, interactions with the end-users and the research results. The blogs will be shared on our website as well as linked to the interactive map of the '[Arctic Window](#)~~Windows to the Arctic~~'.

Media package and press releases: GRID-Arendal will produce a media package that will complement periodic press releases associated with major outputs of Arctic PASSION. The media package will consist of expert contacts, visual material free to use, logos, and designated media contact for the project. The press releases will be coordinated at the Project Management Office and developed with the communication departments of the Arctic PASSION partners, which will use their respective channels for dissemination (e.g. Alphasigaleo or EurekaAlert!) in addition to the Arctic PASSION channels.

The media package will be launched by the beginning of 2022 and updated regularly. GRID-Arendal will also create a folder on the website linked through the Contact page for royalty-free

photos that journalists, researchers and others can use. All Arctic PASSION partners will be invited to contribute photos to this album.

Summer schools & training workshops: Arctic PASSION will develop a storytelling and media training workshop for early-career scientists that are further elaborated under the Arctic PASSION Training and Education Plan.

“Arctic Window~~Windows to the Arctic~~” platform: GRID-Arendal will lead the development of the “Arctic Window~~Windows to the Arctic~~” website – an interactive online gateway to Arctic PASSION Pilot Services and other relevant Arctic information such as Arctic Copernicus data (‘The Arctic window of Copernicus’). The website will be co-developed with various stakeholders and rights holders to make it a useful tool for the end-users. [Arctic Window~~Windows to the Arctic~~](#) will include an interactive multimedia platform incorporating Indigenous, local and traditional knowledge, and scientific data. The aim is to increase the overall impact of Arctic PASSION by providing information about the societal and economic value of an Arctic observing network and links to the Pilot Services and by increasing ownership and usage of the services by stakeholders via co-creation of various elements for the platform. The platform will be co-developed by the Pilot Service developers, Early Career Researchers, Indigenous and local knowledge holders and community members. The elements may consist of animations, comics, videos, or dissemination products in other digital formats. [Arctic Window~~Windows to the Arctic~~](#) and the multimedia platform can be accessed through the Arctic PASSION website.

European project-related platforms: such as [CORDIS](#), [EUROGOOS](#), [Copernicus](#)

European Commission knowledge transfer tools: such as Research and Innovation success stories, CORDIS, Horizon Dashboard, Horizon Results Booster, Innovation Radar, Horizon Results Platform).

Event Activities, booths: We will cooperate with other EU Polar Cluster projects (Work Package 6) to promote Arctic PASSION with joint booths at events, and feature Arctic PASSION prominently at several venues and high-level meetings, examples listed in table 2. We will host side events, sessions, booths and/or implement workshops either in conjunction with these activities or side by side. We will also organise tailored events and briefings for the members of the European Parliament. This list will be updated constantly and synchronised with the project calendar available on the Intranet.

Table 2. Initial mapping of relevant upcoming events of interest to Arctic PASSION (will be updated regularly) - the same table featured in the Communication Plan.

Event	Role/Institutions present (if known)	Date (if known)	Frequency if applicable
Arctic Frontiers		End of January	Yearly
Arctic Observing Summit		End of March	Bi-annually
Arctic Science Summit Week		End of March	
EGU General Assembly		End of April yearly	Yearly
EuroGEO Annual meeting/conference		May	
GEO Symposium		mid-June	
International Conference on Permafrost (ICOP)		mid-June	
Polar Data Forum		end of September	
Arctic Circle		October	Yearly
European Polar Science Week	EU Cluster representation	October	
European Conference on Permafrost (EUCOP)		end of October	
GEO Week		November	
EU Arctic Forum and Indigenous Peoples' dialogue in Brussels	Participation by Project Office	10-11 Nov	one-time event
GTN-P		mid-November	
Polar Data Architecture workshop		end of November	
IASS workshop on Ethics and Methods in Arctic Transformative Research	AWI-Arctic Office presentation	25-26 November 2021	one-time event
Sharing Circle on Arctic wildland fires (from CAFF and EPPR Working Groups of the Arctic Council)		17-18 November 2021	one-time event
Arctic Council Senior Arctic Official meetings	Presentation by the Arctic Office on Arctic PASSION	1-2 December 2021	twice a year

AGU Fall Meeting	Scientific presentation by Arctic PASSION partners	mid-December	Yearly
IMO workshops		ongoing	
Arctic Council Working Group Meetings		TBC	1-2 times a year
EU Polar Cluster meetings		TBC	Monthly
ESA Polar Cluster meetings			yearly

3. Main Tasks and Responsibilities in dissemination and utilisation

3.1 Partner Responsibilities & timeline

Arctic PASSION work packages will engage with dissemination and Utilisation activities that are most relevant for their themes. Table 3 provides an overview on the main activities of each work package.

Table 3. Main dissemination and utilisation activities of Arctic PASSION work packages and their leads.

Work package	Lead	Main dissemination & utilisation activity
1: Augment & coordinate Arctic observations	NPI, LU	Papers in peer-reviewed journals
2: Improving Arctic Data System	MET Norway, AWI	Papers in peer-reviewed journals
3: Optimizing the Arctic Observation Network	MET Norway, OASys	Papers in peer-reviewed journals
4: Euro GEO Pilot Services	Snowchange, GCRC	Rights- and stakeholder engagement events, Pilot Services, Dialogues
5: Assessing Societal benefits	JRC, FMI	Assessing results impact
6: Clustering and international collaboration	FMI, UKRI-BAS	Policy Briefs, Dialogue platforms, Event activities, booths
7: Policy and decision-making support	AWI-Arctic Office, AMAP	Policy Briefs, Dialogues, Survey, Fact Sheet on Arctic Observing Systems
8: Co-developing a unified pan-AOSS	AWI, UKRI-BAS	Policy Briefs, Dialogue platforms, White papers, reports

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9: Linking Arctic observing network with society	AWI-APECS, GRID-Arendal	Website, " Arctic Window Windows to the Arctic " platform, social media, flyers, stakeholder events, training, newsletter, surveys
10: Project Management	AWI	Ensure the timely delivery of project deliverables according to the work plan; Organise and prepare the General Assemblies and support the organisation of other project meetings

4. Risks and barriers to Utilisation and their mitigation

There are certain risks and barriers that could potentially influence Utilisation of the Arctic PASSION results (Table 4). Arctic PASSION will assess and monitor them and frequently update strategies to mitigate them.

Table 4. Mitigation strategy of risks and barriers to Utilisation of the results.

Risk or barrier	Mitigation strategy
Basic deliverables necessary for following tasks are delivered late or incomplete- Medium	The SG and the PMO are very experienced in managing large consortiums and closely follow the work plan. The WP leads regularly monitor task progress and reporting. Bi-weekly telecoms with the SG keep track of progress and deadlines.
The quality of deliverables is unsatisfying - Low	Arctic PASSION agreed on a quality assurance plan to define the structure and quality of deliverables. The SG critically reviews all deliverables before submission. Details can be found in D10.1.
The conflict between policy process timelines and project results - Medium	Arctic PASSION will ensure that research results (and adequate resources) are available before committing engagement in specific policy processes.
A lack of stakeholder interest, engagement or understanding for Pan-Arctic AOSS work - Low	Arctic PASSION will involve stakeholders in regular meetings and through effective communication ensure a good understanding of the process and desired outcomes and benefits to the stakeholders. International partners and rights- and stakeholders are involved in all project phases from the outset. They are also part of the project management structure as

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	members of the AB and as guests at GA. Partners are very experienced in stakeholder engagement. Many partners, such as SNOW, GINR, INPO, DMI, FMI, AMAP, AINA are very experienced collaborating with rights- and stakeholders. We implemented an Ethics Board to help resolve any/all cultural misunderstandings and ethical conflict.
The unplanned, extended absence of a WP lead - Low	All WPs have a lead + co-lead to ensure the smooth running of the project.
Constraints due to Covid-19 or other global issues (i.e. Community and project meetings in WP4 delayed/cancelled due to COVID) - High	Arctic PASSION will monitor the situation and take appropriate mitigation measures, including holding online meetings; close dialogue with the EU will be maintained concerning delays in research plans.

5. Impact monitoring and reporting

The project is required to submit details on the following indicators every 6 months for reporting to the EU. It is the responsibility of each individual project member who has contributed any publication, communication or dissemination activity to report on it themselves through an easily available log sheet on the intranet. However, it is the responsibility of each Work Package lead to ensure that their members have completed this information, and it is the responsibility of the Project Management Office to collect and submit these to the EU:

- Number of publications
- Number of citations from Arctic PASSION publications
- Number of press releases
- Participation in conferences
- Participation in workshops
- Participation in any other kinds of events
- Primary audience reached
- Secondary audience reached
- Estimated number of persons reached
- Number of co-created outputs of the project, for Indigenous People's communities and local communities

However, the following key performance indicators (Table 5) have been identified specifically for Arctic PASSION's dissemination and Utilisation activities, as well as roles and responsibilities for monitoring them. Arctic PASSION will monitor these indicators bi-annually in order to evaluate the effectiveness of the strategies and tools. Adjustments to these will be made if needed.

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Commented [3]: This is not required by EU so I don't think it needs to be on this list. However, it is great if we can report more on this topic.

Table 5. Arctic PASSION Key Performance Indicators for dissemination and utilisation.

Specific indicator	Roles/Responsibilities
Number of downloads of dissemination products, estimated readership.	WP9 with input from partners.
Number of data downloads.	WP9 with input from partners.
Number of people participating in workshops, knowledge transfer or dissemination events.	Project Office with support from all partners, collated by WP9.
<u>Documentation of reaching specific target audiences such as Indigenous Youth in the events or other direct interactions.</u>	<u>Partners working with specific target groups with support from WP9 and Project Office</u>
User feedback on quality and design of products targeted at different audiences.	All partners responsible for keeping testimonials (e.g. written emails or other) expressing user feedback–will be collated by WP9.
Appearance or mention of Arctic PASSION research results or recommendations in policy documents and or documents informing policy processes ranging from local to global.	All partners responsible for monitoring where relevant, WP9 will collate.
Number of publications, number of citations, number of reads and downloads from preprint repositories (e.g. journal websites, ResearchGate). Citations will also be tracked on Google Scholar.	Project Office, all partners responsible for reporting their publications, WP9 will collate.
Evidence of transfer of research and innovation into practice (patents, prototypes, licenses).	Project Office and Lead Team based on input from partners.
Documented instances where the project has had an influence on Indigenous <u>Peoples'</u> and local community members. <u>there has been a process of co-creation.</u> <u>Feedback on whether co-creation process it was meaningful.</u>	All partners but especially WP4. WP9 will collate.